

Benefit Linkage Models for Rural Clean Energy Transition under Rural Revitalization in China

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Abstract

Against the backdrop of rural revitalization and the green transition of rural energy, and in conjunction with relevant national policies from 2019 to 2025, this paper points out that the core issue in the current promotion of rural clean energy lies in the imperfect benefit linkage mechanism, along with problems such as inadequate infrastructure, lack of operation and maintenance, and over-reliance on subsidies. Based on differences in driving forces of benefits, the benefit linkage models for rural clean energy are categorized into five types: policy-driven models, production-investment models, energy storage innovation models, demand-led models, and platform integration models. The paper also analyzes deficiencies in the new energy industry, including management systems, industrial ecology, technological costs, and mismatches between resources and load. Finally, it proposes pathways for "policy coordination, technological standardization, farmer empowerment, and equitable distribution" to transform farmers from "bystanders" to "beneficiaries" in the energy transition, thereby achieving synergistic progress with rural revitalization.

Keywords: *Rural clean energy, Benefit linkage mechanism, Rural revitalization.*

JEL Classification codes: *O13, O18, P18.*

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Introduction

Energy is the foundation for the development of a country and a nation. Rural areas are a key region for national development and possess a large amount of renewable energy. The General Secretary pointed out: "In implementing the rural revitalization strategy, a key task for promoting green development in China's rural areas in the new era is to adopt green development methods and lifestyles." "The promotion of clean energy in rural areas has become an important path to achieving rural revitalization and sustainable development. In 2019, it was proposed to accelerate

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the promotion of clean energy heating in northern regions: action plans for the governance of scattered coal in rural areas and the "coal-to-electricity" and "coal-to-gas" transformation were put forward to reduce the utilization of non-renewable energy sources such as fossil fuels (NBN, 2019)**Error! Reference source not found.** In 2020, the General Office of the Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Affairs issued the "Key Points of Work on Agriculture, Rural Areas, Science, Education, Environment and Energy in 2020" (No. 3 of the General Office of the Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Affairs [2020]), which directly guided localities to develop rural biomass energy and solar energy in accordance with local conditions. It focused on promoting technical models such as straw baling direct combustion, biogas heating, and solar energy utilization, and supported the construction of rural multi-energy complementary demonstration projects. It provides a clear path for the implementation of clean energy for rural revitalization (Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Affairs, 2020). In 2021, in response to the national rural revitalization strategy, a new type of rural energy system was built in rural areas to fully utilize the spatial resources and energy storage resources in rural areas (Yin, Wang, & Zhang, 2025). In the report of the 20th National Congress of the Communist Party of China in 2022, the Chairperson once again emphasized the significance of comprehensively promoting rural revitalization in the section on accelerating the building of a new development pattern and focusing on promoting high-quality development. He proposed to deeply implement the consolidation and improvement project of rural power grids, promote the construction of clean energy such as rural photovoltaic and biomass energy, and consolidate the achievements of the photovoltaic poverty alleviation project. Develop the photovoltaic industry in poverty-stricken areas where conditions permit (The 14th Five-Year Plan for Renewable Energy Development., 2022). In 2023, we will promote the construction of pilot counties for the rural energy revolution, and drive the high-quality development of clean energy in rural areas at the county level (National Energy Administration & other ministries, 2023). Promote renewable energy technologies, enhance the level of rural energy infrastructure, and formulate and introduce subsidy policies for clean energy use in rural areas. In 2024, the "Thousand Towns and Ten Thousand Villages Wind Power Initiative" will be launched, encouraging the sharing of wind power project benefits through legal means such as land use rights shareholding, exploring new models of rural energy cooperation, and promoting the formation of a multi-energy complementary comprehensive energy system in rural areas (Li, 2024). The Energy Law of the People's Republic of China came into effect on January 1, 2025. For the first time, hydrogen energy was incorporated into the energy management system, establishing its status as an energy source. The legislative goals were to promote high-quality energy development, ensure national energy security, and facilitate green and low-carbon economic and social development. In recent years, the consumption of fossil energy has been increasing year by year (The Energy Law of the People's Republic of China, 2025).

By the end of December 2023, the total installed capacity of renewable energy power generation in the country had reached 1.516 billion kilowatts, accounting for 51.9% of the total installed capacity of power generation in the country (Yin, et al., 2024). Among them, solar photovoltaic power generation accounted for three quarters and became the absolute main force. In 2023, the growth rate of installed capacity of photovoltaic power generation was 55.2%, and that of power generation was 36.7%, both reaching the highest levels in history (Zhang, et al., 2025). With the transformation of the energy structure, in 2023, the installed capacity of renewable clean energy such as wind and solar power in China reached 1.47 billion kilowatts, accounting for over 50% of the country's total installed capacity of power generation, and for the first time surpassed the installed capacity of thermal power (National Energy Administration, 2024). The core issue lies in the imperfect interest connection mechanism: there is a lack of stable cooperative ties among entities such as farmers, enterprises, the government, and research institutions, which leads to widespread phenomena such as "emphasizing development over sharing" and "emphasizing investment over benefits" (Han, 2020). The infrastructure is not well-developed. Apart from the

relatively complete power supply, other energy sources have not been fully popularized in rural areas. Rural residents rely heavily on non-commercial energy, and the degree of commercial utilization of energy is not high (Shu, & Xu, 2022). Meanwhile, after the installation of energy projects in rural areas, there are no maintenance personnel in the later stage, resulting in the idleness and abandonment of energy projects, and the corresponding supporting facilities are not complete enough (The 14th Five-Year Plan for Advancing Agricultural and Rural Modernization, 2022). Rural solar microgrids and photovoltaic poverty alleviation projects have long been constrained by high operation and maintenance costs and reliance on subsidies. Many farmers rely on subsidies to use clean energy (Hu, & Qiao, 2025). Now is a crucial stage for the comprehensive revitalization of rural areas, which brings new requirements and challenges to the development and application of clean energy in rural areas. How to strengthen the cooperation model of rural energy and further improve the development and utilization of rural energy has become the focus of scholars' attention at present. This article studies the main cooperation models of rural clean energy and how to develop rural clean energy cooperation.

Main Models of Rural Energy Cooperation

The No. 1 Central Document of 2023 proposes that we will comprehensively promote rural revitalization, intensify the development of agricultural science and technology, drive high-quality development of rural industries, and build beautiful villages. To accelerate the modernization of rural areas, it is necessary to optimize the energy supply structure in rural areas. The "14th Five-Year Plan for Promoting Modernization of Agriculture and Rural Areas" points out that to strengthen the construction of clean energy in rural areas, it is necessary to promote the development of photovoltaic and wind power in rural areas in a way that suits local conditions and advance the diversified utilization of rural biomass energy (The 14th Five-Year Plan for Advancing Agricultural and Rural Modernization, 2022). China's renewable and clean energy has formed a diversified clean energy supply system including photovoltaic, wind power and hydropower, which is the main model of rural energy cooperation (Tang, W., Wang, Z., & Zhang, L. (2024): A diversified clean energy supply system should comprehensively optimize the energy structure and promote the innovative development of clean energy. We must adhere to the principle of giving priority to ecological conservation and pursuing green development, deepen the structural reform on the energy supply side, and intensify efforts to break through key technologies for clean energy (Zhang, et al., 2023).

Based on the differences in the sources of interest driving forces, the interest connection models of rural clean energy in China can be classified into five major categories: policy-driven type dominated by external pulling forces, production and investment type dominated by internal pushing forces, and energy storage innovation type, demand-led type, and platform integration type dominated by value pulling forces (Fang, & Li, 2024).

Policy-Driven

National policies guide and promote the development of rural energy cooperatives, and adopt policy tools such as laws, regulations and government subsidies. Lingyan Li, Fangmei Fan and Xiaodan Liu employed content analysis to construct an analytical framework for rural energy policies, starting from both policy tools and policy goals (Yin, et al., 2024). Based on this framework, conduct quantitative analysis of relevant policies and propose specific paths and methods for optimizing the rural energy policy system. The state clarifies the legal status and operational rules of rural energy cooperatives through laws and regulations, providing institutional guarantees for their development. Meanwhile, the government encourages farmers to participate in the construction and operation of rural energy cooperatives through subsidy policies. These

subsidy policies not only reduce the economic burden on farmers but also enhance their enthusiasm for participating in clean energy projects. For instance, the government provides financial subsidies to farmers who install photovoltaic panels, which makes more farmers willing to install photovoltaic equipment, thereby promoting the use of clean energy in rural areas (Zhao, & Lei, 2024). In the process of policy implementation, the establishment and development of rural energy cooperatives have become a key link. The establishment of cooperatives should comply with the requirements of national policies and also take into account the actual local conditions. Local governments have played a significant role in the establishment of cooperatives, helping them smoothly carry out clean energy projects by providing financial support and technical guidance. These projects not only optimize the rural energy structure but also promote the sustainable development of the rural economy (Jiang, et al., 2024).

In addition, the research of Lingyan Li, Fangmei Fan and Xiaodan Liu also points out that the selection and application of policy tools need to be closely integrated with policy goals (Yin, et al., 2024). Laws and regulations provide a stable institutional environment for rural energy cooperatives, while government subsidies directly encourage farmers' participation. Through quantitative analysis, they found that an effective combination of policy tools could significantly enhance the effectiveness of policy implementation. Therefore, optimizing the rural energy policy system requires establishing a closer connection between policy tools and policy goals to ensure that policies can truly promote the sustainable development of rural energy (Liu, 2024).

By the end of 2020, the distributed photovoltaic energy cooperative project in rural areas and towns of County A, Jiangxi Province, had cumulatively completed a photovoltaic installed capacity of 150MW based on the implementation of photovoltaic power generation projects in rural energy cooperatives. The photovoltaic power generation project of the rural energy cooperative in County A involves three major participants: farmers, the government, and the power grid company. The project is led by the power grid company as the overall leading party, which signs cooperation agreements with farmers to lease their idle land. The construction of photovoltaic power generation panels in County A has provided employment opportunities for farmers, brought substantial profits and income to the power grid company, established a good reputation for the local government, promoted the optimization and adjustment of the local energy structure, facilitated the consumption of clean energy, and achieved the goal of common prosperity for rural groups (He, et al., 2022).

Figure 1. Policy Analysis Framework Diagram

Production Investment Type

The production investment model is a mode in which enterprises or investors take the lead and promote the development of clean energy through investment, construction and operation of clean energy projects. This model emphasizes market mechanisms and investment returns. Entities form close cooperative relationships through capital, technology or land investment, and rely on internal driving forces to maintain connections. The main model is the shareholding cooperative system. Under the shareholding cooperative system, farmers contribute their land and labor to the cooperative, forming a community of "shared benefits and risks", and share dividends constitute the core income (Jiang, et al., 2024).

For instance, "One Village, One Factory" is a typical example. The government invests fiscal funds to build biomass fuel processing plants in villages and entrusts professional contractors to manage and operate them through contracts. Farmers can purchase processed clean fuel at a price lower than the market price by providing the biomass raw materials such as straw they have collected to the factory in accordance with the agreement. The government will also provide subsidies to farmers who purchase biomass heating furnaces, thus forming a tripartite cooperation mechanism of "government guidance - enterprise operation - farmer participation". This model clearly defines the rights and responsibilities of each subject, concentrating the scattered resources of farmers to form a large-scale supply capacity and reducing the transaction costs when promoting clean energy (Wen, et al, 2022).

Another representative one is the "photovoltaic roof rental model". As the investor, the solar leasing company bears all the costs of the rooftop photovoltaic system, including design, equipment purchase and installation. The company will sign long-term lease contracts with farmers and pay them roof usage fees every year. During the contract period, the company holds the ownership of the equipment and is responsible for its maintenance. After the contract expires, the equipment will belong to the farmer. This model lowers the financial threshold for farmers to participate in clean energy projects by separating property rights and designing income distribution methods. It also ensures that enterprises can obtain the expected investment returns through market mechanisms, thus effectively integrating farmers' enthusiasm with the macro energy transition goals (Zhang, et al., 2024).

Figure 2. Model Diagram of Shareholding Cooperative System

Energy Storage Innovation

Energy storage innovation refers to promoting the development of clean energy through technological innovation. The core of energy storage innovation (value attraction) lies in enhancing resource utilization efficiency, creating incremental value and optimizing distribution through technological innovation and business model innovation. The shared energy storage model decouples ownership from usage rights to achieve efficient resource utilization and cost sharing. The distribution of the integrated energy system is achieved through the Nash equilibrium algorithm, which balances the interests of multiple parties and rationally distributes the benefits (Huang, 2025).

The energy storage projects in Shandong Province are typical practices. This project achieves efficient resource utilization through centralized energy storage units, addresses the issue of new energy consumption, promotes the stability of the power grid and the development of the new energy industry, and demonstrates the integration of technological innovation and business model innovation. Cooperative games, as a common method for the distribution of interests among multiple subjects, not only emphasizes individual interests but also considers the overall interests. By achieving Nash equilibrium, it can reach the overall optimum (Li, Huang, & Yue, 2022).

Figure 3. Diagram of the Innovative Model for Energy Storage

Demand-Driven Type

Demand-driven type refers to taking the actual energy demands of rural residents as the starting point and promoting the popularization and application of clean energy technologies by meeting their demands for clean, efficient and convenient energy services. This model emphasizes starting from user needs and achieving the sustainable development of clean energy through integration.

In the "coal-to-N" practice in County H, Shanxi Province, rural residents' yearning for convenient, clean and modern heating methods has driven village collectives to choose new energy supply technologies, thus achieving an organic combination of consumption and structural supply. By introducing technological innovations, such as improving internal insulation, low-ambient temperature air-source water heat pumps, and intelligent biomass fuel heating stoves. It has effectively enhanced the utilization efficiency of clean energy in rural areas and the quality of life of residents. This demand-driven mechanism not only enhances the quality of life for rural residents but also promotes the popularization and application of clean energy technologies (Fang, & Li, 2024).

Figure 4. Demand Leading Model Diagram

Platform Integration Type

The platform integration type of the clean energy interest connection model refers to achieving collaborative cooperation among multiple stakeholders by building a platform that integrates technology, capital, resources and market. This model emphasizes the application of the platform economy concept, enhancing energy utilization efficiency and economic benefits through means such as multi-energy complementarity, optimized energy dispatching, and energy trading.

In some rural areas, by building photovoltaic power stations, not only clean energy is provided for agricultural greenhouses, but also an integrated development model of "photovoltaic + agriculture + tourism" is achieved through agricultural planting and tourism sightseeing under the photovoltaic panels. For instance, Zhangdai Village in Xihu Town, Yanggu County, has built a photovoltaic power station, which not only provides clean energy for agricultural greenhouses but also realizes an integrated development model of "photovoltaic + agriculture + tourism" through agricultural planting and tourism sightseeing under the photovoltaic panels. This model not only enhances energy utilization efficiency but also boosts local farmers' income and employment, promoting the sustainable development of the rural economy (Tang, Wang, & Zhang, 2024).

Figure 5. Multi-Energy Complementary Platform Diagram

Main Deficiencies in Rural Energy Cooperation

Against the backdrop of the comprehensive advancement of China's rural revitalization strategy and the transformation and upgrading of rural energy consumption structure, the development of clean energy in rural areas has become an important path to achieving modernization in agriculture and rural areas. Despite the continuous efforts of the state in terms of policy support and financial input, and the inclusion of rural clean energy development in the core topics of ecological civilization construction and rural green development, from the perspective of institutional economics, the collaborative cooperation system for the development characteristics of rural clean energy is still in the construction stage. At present, the development lag of the cooperation mechanism in this field mainly manifests in two aspects: Firstly, at the county-level governance level, a systematic collaborative governance framework has yet to be formed among multiple departments such as agriculture and rural affairs, energy management, and ecological environment. Particularly in the full life cycle management process of projects like household photovoltaic power generation, distributed wind power, and biomass energy development, there are obvious overlapped rights and responsibilities as well as regulatory vacuums. This leads to an extended project implementation period and makes it difficult to fully release the comprehensive benefits. Secondly, at the grassroots implementation level, the cooperation model among village collective organizations, farmers' groups and energy enterprises is still in the exploratory stage. Due to the lack of standardized collaboration norms and institutionalized benefit distribution mechanisms, there are significant transaction costs in project connection and insufficient efficiency in resource integration, which seriously restricts the large-scale expansion and high-quality development process of the rural clean energy industry (Han, 2020).

From the perspective of cooperation, in the early stage of rural clean energy development, due to the release of policy dividends and relatively low entry barriers, various entities such as energy enterprises and local cooperatives were attracted to participate. However, the capabilities and demands of different cooperative entities vary: Some energy enterprises focus on short-term economic benefits while neglecting the actual energy consumption needs in rural areas and long-term operation and maintenance services; The coordination ability of the village collective is weak, making it difficult to effectively connect enterprises with farmers. Farmers lack professional knowledge and the right to speak and often find themselves in a passive position in cooperation. This unbalanced cooperative relationship has led to a prominent contradiction between the repetitive construction of low-end projects and the insufficient supply of high-quality services. It not only causes waste of resources but also makes the sustainability of rural clean energy projects insufficient, weakening the motivation of all parties to continuously participate in cooperation (Shu, & Xu, 2022).

When delving into specific fields, the deficiencies in rural clean energy cooperation exhibit significant sectoral differentiation characteristics. In the field of household photovoltaic systems, the problems of single cooperation models and disconnection of rights and responsibilities are prominent: most projects adopt the "roof leasing" model led by enterprises, where farmers only receive fixed rents and lack the right to share the project's profits, resulting in extremely low cooperation stickiness. During the operation and maintenance stage of the project, disputes often arise between enterprises and farmers due to unclear definition of responsibilities. Enterprises shirk their operation and maintenance responsibilities, while farmers refuse to cooperate with equipment inspections, resulting in some photovoltaic equipment remaining in an inefficient state of operation for a long time.

The supply and demand cooperation in the development of biomass energy (such as biogas projects and the energy utilization of straw) is difficult. On the one hand, the scattered operation of farmers makes it difficult to collect raw materials such as straw and livestock manure. There is a lack of professional cooperative organizations to coordinate the supply of raw materials, and the collection and transportation costs for energy enterprises remain high. On the other hand, there is a lack of

long-term and stable raw material supply agreements between enterprises and farmers. Enterprises often suspend production due to raw material shortages, and farmers also lose their enthusiasm for supply because of unstable raw material sales channels, resulting in a collaborative deadlock where "enterprises lack raw materials and farmers lack sales channels". Meanwhile, the production and sales cooperation mechanism for biomass energy products (such as biogas fertilizer and biomass fuel) is lacking, and the market connection of products is not smooth, which further restricts the project's revenue and the sustainability of cooperation (Yue, 2022).

The development of small hydropower in rural areas is confronted with the cooperative challenge of ecological protection and the coordination of interests among multiple parties. Small hydropower projects involve multiple parties such as development enterprises, village collectives, and farmers along the line. There is a lack of an effective cooperation mechanism in the division of ecological protection responsibilities and the distribution of benefits. Development enterprises often neglect the ecological protection needs of the river basin and fail to consult with village collectives and farmers to formulate ecological restoration plans, which leads to farmers' resistance to the projects. In the distribution of project revenue, the proportion of ecological compensation and revenue sharing received by village collectives and farmers is too low, failing to fully enjoy the dividends of clean energy development, which leads to the easy breakdown of the cooperative relationship. In addition, in the technical renovation projects of existing small hydropower stations, the cooperation between enterprises and local governments as well as financial institutions is insufficient, and it is difficult to raise renovation funds, which further hinders their transformation to an eco-friendly model (He, 2024).

The core cooperative contradiction in the development of small rural wind power lies in the imbalance between resource utilization and benefit sharing. Most of the areas rich in rural wind energy resources in our country are in remote mountainous regions. In the development of small wind power projects in these areas, there are obvious deficiencies in the land lease cooperation between energy enterprises and village collectives and farmers: the land compensation standards are not uniform, and the opinions of farmers have not been fully solicited, which often leads to land disputes. The power generation income of the project has not established a linkage and sharing mechanism with the village collective and farmers. Farmers only receive one-time land compensation, and it is difficult for them to share the fruits of clean energy development in the long term. Meanwhile, the grid connection cooperation between small wind power projects and power grid enterprises is not smooth. The approval process for grid access is cumbersome, and the cross-regional dispatching collaboration mechanism is lacking. The phenomenon of wind power curtailment is still prominent, further reducing the enthusiasm of all parties to participate in the cooperation (Recent Development Status of Small and Medium Wind Power Industries, 2016).

Overall, the current rural clean energy cooperation system is still constrained by multiple systemic deficiencies: At the level of the collaboration mechanism, the cross-departmental and cross-subject cooperation framework is not yet complete, and there is a lack of a unified coordination platform and rules, resulting in low cooperation efficiency; At the level of benefit distribution, the mechanism for sharing benefits among various entities is not perfect. Grassroots entities such as farmers and village collectives benefit less and lack the motivation to cooperate. At the technical service level, the technical cooperation between energy enterprises and research institutions as well as farmers is disconnected. Farmers lack the skills to operate and maintain equipment, and enterprises do not provide continuous technical training, resulting in weak project operation and maintenance capabilities. At the policy guarantee level, the implementation effect of rural clean energy cooperation support policies is affected by the differences in local enforcement intensity. Some policies lack specific guidance on cooperative relationships and are difficult to solve practical collaboration problems (Wang, 2019).

Discussion

The innovation of the rural clean energy benefit connection model hinges on seizing the four key paths of "policy coordination, technical standardization, farmer subjectivity, and fair distribution". It is necessary to strengthen institutional design, deepen shareholding cooperation and lower the participation threshold, so that farmers can transform from "bystanders" of energy transition to direct "beneficiaries". Only in this way can energy transition and rural revitalization develop together. Shareholding cooperation can be deepened, the "guaranteed income + floating dividend" model can be promoted, the "energy + agriculture" scenario can be developed, and cooperatives can be encouraged to take the lead in operation (Shi, et al., 2024). This will enhance farmers' participation and income. Formulate technical standards, upgrade power grid facilities, and promote the "microgrid + energy storage" system to enhance the technological level and infrastructure of clean energy in rural areas. Establish special loans, explore the "zero down payment + installment repayment of income" model, strengthen capacity building, take advantage of the "familiar person society" effect, thereby enhancing farmers' enthusiasm for participation, promote the BOT model, ensure fair distribution, and establish a third-party auditing mechanism to ensure the reasonable distribution of funds and income (Yu, et al., 2022).

First of all, policy coordination should combine policy guidance with market mechanisms to promote the transformation of rural energy. Encourage farmers to participate in clean energy projects such as photovoltaic and energy storage through policies to increase their income. At the same time, policies should be flexible and adaptable to the resources and demands of different regions.

Secondly, technological standardization relies on technological progress to better integrate energy transition with rural revitalization. Technologies such as digital control and distributed energy integration can enhance energy utilization efficiency and management levels. Moreover, technical standardization can reduce project costs and make farmers more willing to participate.

In addition, the subjectification of farmers should be achieved through shareholding cooperation, interest connection and other means, enabling farmers to benefit from the energy transition. For instance, promoting the integration model of "energy + industry" can transform farmers from mere energy producers into energy users and managers, enhancing their sense of participation and gain.

Moreover, the fairness of distribution depends on the joint efforts of policies, market mechanisms and financial tools to ensure that the fruits of energy transition are distributed fairly. For instance, by leveraging methods such as agricultural carbon trading and green finance, farmers can gain more benefits from clean energy projects (Xu, & Tong, 2011).

Conclusions and Implications

China is a vast country with abundant reserves of new energy, laying a solid foundation for the development of new energy resources in our country. Hydropower, solar energy, wind energy and biomass energy belong to the green energy industry and are important components of the green, low-carbon and circular economic system, as well as significant measures for building an ecological civilization. Under the backdrop of China's efforts to achieve the goals of carbon peaking and carbon neutrality, the energy and power system is transforming towards cleanliness and low-carbonization. This requires leveraging the clean energy attributes of hydropower, as well as its advantages in large-capacity rapid emergency response and energy storage power regulation.

At present, the development of new energy in our country still faces many practical challenges, which urgently need to be highly valued by relevant departments and units. The phenomenon of "regulatory gaps" at the management level urgently needs to be addressed. Measures such as optimizing the energy development structure and strengthening regulatory efforts should be taken to effectively alleviate the pressure of energy supply shortages and provide strong support for high-quality economic and social development. Meanwhile, ecological and environmental protection has put forward more stringent requirements for energy development, and it is rather difficult to coordinate the interests and demands of multiple development entities in a comprehensive manner. In addition, the continuous rise in the threshold for technological research and development, the persistently high construction costs, the increasing complexity of resettlement work, and the superimposition of risks in the river basin system are intertwined, collectively constituting systematic factors that restrict the sustainable development of the energy industry.

The development situation and external environment of energy exploitation are undergoing profound changes. The traditional development concepts and paths are no longer suitable for the new development requirements, and there is an urgent need to innovate the core concepts and implementation paths of energy development. Energy development should be placed at the strategic height of promoting the supply-side structural reform of energy and transforming the mode of energy development. At the same time, it should be regarded as a key measure to assist the revitalization of underdeveloped regions, advance ecological civilization construction and the practice of a beautiful China.

Author Contributions

Conceptualization, Z.A.J., Y.S. and Z.R.R.; methodology, Z.A.J., Y.S. and Z.R.R.; software, Z.A.J., Y.S. and Z.R.R.; validation, Z.A.J., Y.S. and Z.R.R.; writing—original draft preparation, Z.A.J., Y.S. and Z.R.R.; writing—review and editing, Z.A.J., Y.S. and Z.R.R.. All authors agreed to the manuscript.

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Data Availability Statement

The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Informed Consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

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